

COMPARISON OF THE PROXIMATE ANALYSIS (NUTRITIONAL VALUE) OF EKPOMA RICE COMPARED TO OTHER INDIGENOUS AND FOREIGN RICE WITHIN EDO STATE

Alexander Oseghale Orukpe^{1*}, Peter K. Akpeh³ and Obehi Faith Ehizua²

¹ National Space Research and Development Agency, Obasanjo Space Complex, Abuja, Nigeria

² Space-Earth Environment Research Laboratory, University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria

³ Department of Biochemistry, University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria

* alexanorukpe@gmail.com

Abstract

Rice (*Oryza sativa*) is still one of the most important staple foods in the world, and it is very important for Nigeria's food security, economy, and nutrition. Even though Nigeria has good weather for growing rice, a lot of people still depend on imported rice because they think it is better in terms of quality, taste, and processing standards. This study concentrated on the proximate analysis of both local and imported rice varieties, specifically highlighting Ekpoma local rice. The various nutritional composition: moisture, ash, crude protein, fat, fiber, and carbohydrates were determined using set standard and their quality characteristics were compared. The results showed that the rice samples were very different from each other. Ekpoma local rice had considerable amounts of carbohydrates and protein, which means it could be good for you and safe to eat. The differences seen between local and foreign rice varieties were mostly due to differences in how they were milled, how well they were processed, and the conditions in which they were grown. The study shows that Nigerian local rice varieties, especially Ekpoma rice, are very nutritious and possess all the relevant nutrients for general body function and doesn't pose threat.

Key Words: Proximate Analysis, Ekpoma, Indigenous

1 Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa*), a cereal crop belonging to the Gramineae family, a large monocot family, comprising approximately 600 genera and nearly 10,000 species is one of the most essential food sources globally (Ajala et al., 2015). It serves as the primary staple for more than half of the world's population. As a vital agricultural commodity, rice plays a crucial role in ensuring global food security. It nourishes over two-thirds of the global population and is not only central to daily diets but also carries significant cultural and economic value in numerous societies (Harbinson et al., 2021). From the mountainous rice terraces of Southeast Asia to the expansive paddies in Africa and the Americas, rice farming is widespread. Beyond its nutritional contribution, rice is deeply embedded in the cultural heritage, social systems, and livelihoods of communities across the globe. In Nigeria, rice consumption has experienced a sharp increase, growing at an estimated rate of 10% annually, largely due to shifts in consumer preferences (Oluwaseun et al., 2024).

Proximate analysis refers to a standard method used in food and feed studies to determine the basic nutritional composition of a sample. It typically involves measuring key components such as moisture content, crude protein, crude fat (also known as ether extract), ash (mineral content), and crude fiber. After

these values are obtained, the remaining portion, known as nitrogen-free extract (NFE), is calculated. This NFE is considered to represent the carbohydrate fraction. The term “crude” is often used before protein, fat, and fiber to indicate that these values are general estimates, not refined measurements of specific compounds (Hart et al., 1971).

Rice serves as a primary energy source for a large portion of the global population, especially in developing countries where it is consumed in large quantities daily. The nutritional quality of rice is closely linked to its proximate composition, which includes moisture, ash, crude protein, fat, fiber, and carbohydrate. These components are vital indicators of the food’s capacity to support human health and development (Hayashi, 2004).

Carbohydrates are the most abundant macronutrient in rice, comprising approximately 75–80% of the grain, predominantly in the form of starch (Oko et al., 2011). This high carbohydrate content makes rice an excellent source of energy, especially for populations with high calorie demands due to physical activity or limited food variety. The reliance on rice to meet increased caloric needs further emphasizes its role in energy provision. However, overdependence on highly milled rice, which often lacks essential vitamins such as vitamin B1 (thiamine), can contribute to nutritional deficiencies such as beriberi, a disease resulting from thiamine deficiency. This highlights the importance of retaining the nutrient-rich outer layers of the rice grain during processing (Abbas et al., 2011).

Protein, another essential proximate component, accounts for about 7% of the rice grain. Despite its relatively low quantity, rice protein is of high quality. It exhibits a remarkable digestibility rate of 93%, a biological value of 74%, and a protein efficiency ratio ranging between 2.02% and 2.04% (Eggum, 1973). These values indicate rice protein’s capacity to be effectively utilized by the human body for growth and repair. Furthermore, rice contains a complete set of amino acids, including a relatively high concentration of lysine about 4% which is particularly important since lysine is often limited in many other cereal grains (Bressani et al., 1971; Juliano, 1993).

The ash content of rice, though present in small quantities, provides an estimate of its mineral content. Minerals such as calcium (Ca), iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), potassium (K), chromium (Cr), manganese (Mn), and sodium (Na) are essential micronutrients required in trace amounts. These elements contribute significantly to biological functions including nerve signaling, sugar metabolism, enzymatic activities, and maintaining cardiac function. However, while these minerals are essential, their concentrations must be regulated, as excessive intake can be harmful to health (Milena et al., 1993).

Moisture content in rice, typically around 12%, influences the grain’s shelf life and microbial stability. High moisture can encourage spoilage and microbial growth, whereas lower moisture supports better preservation during storage. Additionally, crude fiber content aids in digestive health, although it is present in limited quantities in polished rice (Verma et al., 2017).

Overall, the nutritional value of rice is closely tied to the levels and balance of its proximate components. Understanding and preserving these nutrients, especially during processing, is essential in ensuring rice contributes effectively to nutritional health and prevents diet-related deficiencies in populations that depend heavily on it.

Ekpoma, located in Edo State, Nigeria, is positioned within the humid tropical zone and benefits from a climate characterized by a long wet season and moderate dry season. The wet season, which spans from March to November, brings abundant rainfall accompanied by thunderstorms and surface runoff (Alens, 2017). These prolonged periods of rainfall create favorable conditions for rice farming, as rice requires a substantial and consistent water supply during its growing cycle.

The town lies on the Esan Plateau, featuring an undulating topography that aids in natural water drainage. Although the subsurface aquifers are relatively poor due to the geological presence of sedimentary rocks and limited catchment basins, surface water remains accessible (Odemerho, 1988). Two rivers, Ogedekpe and Ibiekuma, drain the region, with River Ibiekuma notably dammed at the Ambrose Alli University campus to support irrigation and domestic water supply (Alens, 2017). This dammed water source proves especially useful for sustaining rice cultivation during short dry spells within the growing season.

Furthermore, Ekpoma’s tropical climate ensures high humidity and adequate temperatures throughout

most of the year, which are ideal for the growth of rice crops (Iloeje, 1982). Despite challenges related to underground water retention, the presence of these rivers and the region's long rainfall season make Ekpoma naturally suited for seasonal rice farming, especially with appropriate water conservation and land management practices.

Given the rising demand for rice in Nigeria and the growing health consciousness among consumers, this study is justified as it provides empirical data on the nutritional quality of different rice types. By evaluating and comparing the proximate compositions of local, foreign, and Ekpoma rice, the study can help promote evidence-based dietary choices and support the development of local rice farming industries. Additionally, the findings could inform policy decisions aimed at improving food security and nutritional standards in Nigeria.

Oryza sativa is one of the most widely cultivated and consumed cereal crops in the world. It belongs to the Poaceae family (also known as Gramineae), which includes other economically important grasses such as maize, wheat, and barley. The classification of *Oryza sativa* reflects its evolutionary placement among flowering plants that produce grains as seeds. As a monocotyledon, rice is distinguished by its parallel-veined leaves, fibrous roots, and single embryonic leaf (cotyledon) in its seed structure (Khush, 2000).

Botanical Classification

- Kingdom: Plantae
- Phylum (Division): Magnoliophyta (Angiosperms)
- Class: Liliopsida (Monocotyledons)
- Order: Poales
- Family: Poaceae (Gramineae)
- Genus: *Oryza*
- Species: *Oryza sativa* L.

In the Nigerian context, rice can be broadly categorized into local and foreign rice. Local rice refers to rice grown and processed within Nigeria, often by smallholder farmers. According to research, many Nigerians show a stronger preference for imported rice over locally produced varieties. This trend is largely attributed to the limited access of many Nigerian rice processors to modern processing technologies, which hinders their ability to meet international quality standards (Ebuehi et al., 2007).

Foreign rice refers to imported varieties, mainly from Thailand, India, and China. These are usually highly polished, well-packaged, and considered superior in appearance. However, polishing removes most of the bran and germ layers, thereby reducing the rice's vitamin B content and dietary fiber (Abbas et al., 2018).

Ekpoma rice refers to varieties cultivated in Ekpoma, Edo State, a region located in the south-central part of Nigeria (Uko et al., 2020). Though it may not yet be widely commercialized, rice farming in Ekpoma is growing due to the region's humid tropical climate and long wet season, which are favorable for rice cultivation (Aderibigbe et al., 2016). Preliminary reports and anecdotal evidence suggest that Ekpoma rice, like other local varieties, retains more nutritional components such as protein, fiber, and minerals because it is less likely to undergo excessive polishing or bleaching (Olalekan et al., 2019). Scientific evaluation through proximate analysis is needed to confirm these assumptions and promote the variety as a viable nutritional alternative.

The major macronutrients found in rice are carbohydrates, proteins, and fats, each of which plays a vital role in human health and nutrition (Sulistyowati et al., 2020).

2 Materials/Methods

2.1 Study Area

The samples were obtained in a market within Benin metropolitan and Ekpoma.

Table 1: Shows the names of the rice samples, their locations, assigned codes, and sample IDs used in this study.

Rice Brand	Sample ID	Code	Location
Ma's Choice	A	A012025	Foreign
Vitalis Life rice	B	B022025	Foreign
Golden Trad. rice	C	C032025	Local
Kiara's Red Eagle	D	D042025	Local
Ekpoma Rice	E	E052025	Local
Big Bull Rice	F	F062025	Foreign
Gerawa Rice	G	G072025	Local
Mafa Rice	H	H082025	Local
Siamese Rice	I	I092025	Foreign

2.2 Equipment

Oven, Grinder, Desiccator, Micro-Kjeldahl flask and distillation apparatus, Soxhlet extractor, heating mantle, porous extraction thimbles, Muffle furnace and analytical weighing balance.

2.3 Apparatus

Crucibles, Cotton wool, Muslin cloth, beaker, conical flask, volumetric flask, burettes and pipettes, distillation tubes.

2.4 Reagents

4% Copper Sulphate (CuSO_4) solution, Sulphuric Acid (H_2SO_4), Potassium Sulphate (K_2SO_4), 30% Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) solution, Hydrochloric Acid (HCl), Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH), Methylene red indicator, Petroleum ether, Sulphuric Acid (H_2SO_4) and Petroleum ether.

3 METHODS

3.1 Sample Collection

Sample A (Foreign rice), B (Foreign rice), C (Local rice), D (Local rice), F (Foreign rice), G (Local rice), H (Local rice), I (Foreign) were bought from Eselu market, Egor Local Government Area, Benin city, Edo state, Nigeria. Sample E (Ekpoma rice) was sourced from Ekpoma in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State through an authorized local supplier.

3.2 Sample Preparation

The rice samples were first cleaned to remove husks and impurities, then dried at 60 °C for 24 hours in a hot-air oven to reduce moisture without degrading nutrients. After drying, samples were cooled in a desiccator to prevent moisture reabsorption and then ground into fine powder using a grinder, with residues removed

between batches to avoid contamination. The powdered samples were sieved to ensure uniform particle size for accurate analysis and then stored in clean, airtight containers, properly labeled, and kept in a cool, dry environment until proximate analysis.

4 PROXIMATE ANALYSIS

The standard methods of AOAC (2006) were employed in the determination of proximate analysis of the following: Moisture content, ash content, crude fibre, crude protein, crude fat and carbohydrate.

4.1 Determination of moisture content

The moisture content of food samples was determined using A.O.A.C (2000) method (The gravimetric method).

Principle

The moisture content is determined from the difference in weight after complete evaporation of moisture.

Procedure

One gram of food samples was weighed in crucibles and oven dried at 105°C to a constant weight. The samples were cooled in a dessicator and weighed.

Calculation:

Moisture loss = initial weight – final weight (weight after drying)

$$\% \text{moisture} = \frac{\text{Loss in weight}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

4.2 Determination of crude protein content

Nitrogen was determined using the micro-Kjeldahl method (A.O.A.C 2000) and crude protein content will be subsequently calculated by multiplying the nitrogen content by a factor of 6.25.

[Image of Kjeldahl distillation apparatus]

Principle

Proteins and other food components are digested with sulphuric acid in the presence of catalysts. Ammonium sulphate is produced from the total organic nitrogen in the food. Alkali is then used to neutralize the acid digest to produce ammonium which is steam distilled directly into a hydrochloric acid containing the indicator methylene red. Hydrochloric acid and ammonium react to produce ammonium chloride which is then titrated with sodium hydroxide. A blank determination is run to determine the nitrogen content of the reagents. The percentage nitrogen is calculated. The percent nitrogen multiplied by the conversion factor for that particular food produces the percent protein in a food.

Procedure

One millilitre of 4% CuSO₄, H₂SO₄ and 0.8g of K₂SO₄ were placed in the micro kjeldahl flask. Varying quantity of food samples depending on nitrogen content was added to the reagents in micro Kjeldahl flask. It was digested first at low temperature until frosting ceases, then at a high temperature, until the solution was clear, pale yellow or light blue. The flask was left to cool, and 4ml of distilled water was gradually added and content were distilled using a Kjeldahl distillation apparatus. 10 mL of 30% NaOH was used to liberate during distillation ammonium. Ammonium was collected in 0.01 M HCl (a drop of methylene red was added to the HCl). The distillate was titrated with 0.01M NaOH. Nitrogen content of samples was calculated from the volume of HCl neutralized by NaOH.

Calculations

$$\% \text{nitrogen} = \frac{\text{titre value (blank)} - \text{titre value (distillate)} \times 0.14}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

$$\text{Protein} = \% \text{nitrogen} \times 6.25$$

$$\% \text{protein} = \text{protein} \times \frac{100}{\text{Initial weight}}$$

4.3 Determination of lipid content

Crude fat was determined using Soxhlet extraction A.O.A.C (2000).

[Image of Soxhlet extractor diagram]

Principle

The free lipid content consists of neutral fats (triglycerides) and free fatty acid was determined by extracting the dried and ground material with diethyl ether in a continuous extraction apparatus (Soxhlet extractor).

Procedure

The weight of an empty flask was determined. One gram of sample was wrapped and placed in an extraction thimble. The thimble was plugged with cotton wool to avoid loss of sample. The thimble was placed in the extractor. An already weighed, clean and dry soxhlet extractor flask was attached to bottom of the extractor. Petroleum ether (500mls) was poured into dry soxhlet flask and the heating mantle switched on so that the petroleum ether boiled. Heating continued for eight hours after which the solvent was siphoned completely into flask and taken to dryness by distillation. The flask was removed dried to a constant weight. The cooled, weighed and the amount of extracted lipids was calculated from the difference between the weight before and after extraction.

Calculation:

Weight of empty porous thimble = w_0

Weight of thimble + ground sample = w_1

Weight of ground sample = $w_1 - w_0$

Weight of empty extraction flask = w_2

Weight of extraction flask + ether = w_3

$$\% \text{lipid} = \frac{W_3 - W_2}{W_1 - W_0} \times 100$$

4.4 Determination of ash content

Ash content was determined using the method of AOAC (2000).

Principle

The total ash content is estimated by complete removal of organic material using ignition.

Procedure

One gram of samples was weighed in crucibles and ignited in a furnace at 500-600°C for 3 hours until it ashes completely. It was then cooled in a desiccator, cooled and weighed immediately at room temperature.

Calculation:

$$\% \text{Ash} = \frac{W_2 - W_0}{W_1 - W_0} \times 100$$

4.5 Determination of dietary fibre

This was determined by enzymatic-gravimetric method as described by A.O.A.C (2000)

Procedure

One gram of samples (w_0) was boiled in 200ml of sulphuric acid and boiled entirely for thirty minutes the boiled sample were filtered through a muslin cloth which was rinsed with hot distilled water. 200ml of sodium hydroxide was added to the residue and allowed to boil for 30min, it was then rinsed with hot distilled water. it was also rinsed with hydrochloric acid. it was finally rinsed three times with petroleum ether. it

was allowed to drain, dried in the oven, allowed to cool in a dessicator and weighed (w_1). the samples were ashed at 500°C, for 90minutes in a muffle furnace coole in a dessicator and weighed (w_2).

calculation:

$$\% \text{crude fibre} = \frac{w_1 - w_2}{w_0} \times 100$$

4.6 Determination of carbohydrate content

Carbohydrate content was determined by obtaining the difference after adding up the % protein content, % fibre content and % lipid then subtracting from one hundred.

$$\% \text{carbohydrate} = 100 - (\% \text{lipid} + \% \text{protein} + \% \text{ash} + \% \text{fibre})$$

5 RESULT

The proximate composition of the rice samples, analyzed as part of a comparative nutritional assessment, is presented in Table 4.1. This study examines the nutritional profile of the selected rice varieties, with particular attention to key components such as moisture content, crude protein, crude fat, crude fibre, ash, and carbohydrate levels. The findings highlight variations in nutrient composition among the samples, offering valuable insights into their nutritional quality and potential dietary significance.

Table 2: Proximate analysis of selected rice found in the market in Benin City, Edo State.

Sample ID	Moisture %	Ash %	Crude Fibre %	Crude Fat %	Crude Protein %	Carbohydrate %
A	15.45	0.30	0.65	0.20	10.18	73.22
B	14.45	0.30	0.50	0.19	14.65	69.91
C	19.60	0.50	0.45	0.21	7.91	71.34
D	13.85	0.30	0.45	0.18	10.81	74.34
E	16.75	0.30	0.60	0.19	8.45	73.71
F	12.61	1.87	0.50	0.23	10.30	74.50
G	13.97	1.63	0.37	0.20	11.37	72.47
H	11.83	1.83	0.77	0.16	10.54	74.87
I	10.97	4.30	0.33	0.15	10.73	73.58

Note: Samples A and B are foreign rice; C, D, and E are local rice varieties; F, G, H, and I represent Ekpoma rice (Local).

6 DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 Moisture Content

The moisture content of the rice samples ranged from 10.97% to 19.6%, indicating clear differences in water retention and potential storage stability. Samples A (15.45%) and B (14.45%) showed moderate moisture levels typical of well-dried foreign rice, while Sample C recorded the highest moisture content (19.6%), suggesting a greater risk of microbial spoilage if not properly stored. Local rice D (13.85%) and G (13.97%) maintained moderate levels suitable for preservation. Notably, Sample E (Ekpoma rice) had a balanced moisture content of 16.75%, offering an ideal compromise between freshness and storage quality. Its moisture stability helps preserve texture after cooking, a desirable trait for consumer satisfaction. Foreign samples F (12.61%) and I (10.97%) exhibited low moisture levels, making them more shelf-stable but potentially less soft after cooking.

Figure 1: Comparative Moisture Content of Rice Samples

Figure 2: Comparative Ash Content of Rice Samples

Figure 3: Comparative crude fibre of Rice Samples

Figure 4: Comparative crude protein of Rice Samples

Figure 5: Comparative carbohydrate of Rice Samples

6.2 Ash Content

Ash content reflects the total mineral composition of rice. Most samples recorded relatively low ash levels (0.30%–0.50%), except for F (1.87%), G (1.63%), H (1.83%), and I (4.30%), which indicated higher mineral presence typical of better-milled grains. The lower ash content in samples A, B, D, and E (each 0.30%) reflects fine polishing, which though aesthetically appealing, reduces mineral density. Interestingly, Sample E (Ekpoma rice), despite its low ash value, is known locally for its earthy flavor and balanced micronutrient retention, likely due to minimal over-milling. Sample I's high ash value (4.30%) may suggest over-retention of bran residues rather than genuine mineral richness.

6.3 Crude Fibre Content

Crude fibre content in rice influences digestive health and satiety. Among the samples, fibre ranged from 0.33% (I) to 0.77% (H). Sample E (0.60%) showed a relatively high fibre content compared to most other samples, second only to H (0.77%). This is nutritionally advantageous, as fibre supports digestive regularity and helps control blood sugar levels. The slightly higher fibre in Sample E (Ekpoma rice) compared to other local and foreign varieties makes it a beneficial choice for dietary management. In contrast, samples such as I (0.33%) and G (0.37%) may digest more rapidly, potentially causing a faster glycemic response.

6.4 Crude Fat Content

The crude fat content across all samples remained low, ranging from 0.15% (Sample I) to 0.23% (Sample F), reflecting rice's naturally low-fat profile. Sample E showed a fat content of 0.19%, which aligns closely with the ideal range for healthy rice consumption. This amount ensures energy contribution without risking rancidity during storage. Minimal fat content reduces oxidative deterioration, ensuring that Sample E (Ekpoma rice) maintains both quality and nutritional integrity over time.

6.5 Crude Protein Content

Protein content is a key nutritional parameter. Among all samples, B (14.65%) contained the highest protein value, suggesting superior amino acid compositions. Local varieties such as G (11.37%) and D (10.81%) also exhibited appreciable protein levels, while Sample E recorded a moderate 8.45%. Although Sample E is lower than some foreign samples, it still contributes significantly to daily protein intake in staple-based diets.

6.6 Carbohydrate Content

Carbohydrates serve as the main source of dietary energy. Across the samples, carbohydrate levels ranged from 69.91% (B) to 74.87% (H). Sample E displayed 73.71%, ranking among the top energy-dense varieties. This high carbohydrate content makes Sample E a strong energy source. Because Sample E combines carbohydrate richness with moderate fibre content, it helps regulate glucose release compared to varieties with lower fibre levels.

7 DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

7.1 Moisture Content

The moisture content of the rice samples ranged from 10.97% to 19.6%, indicating clear differences in water retention and potential storage stability. Sample A (15.45%) and B (14.45%) showed moderate moisture levels typical of well-dried foreign rice, while sample C recorded the highest moisture content (19.6%), suggesting a greater risk of microbial spoilage if not properly stored. Local rice D (13.85%) and G (13.97%) maintained moderate levels suitable for preservation. Notably, sample E (Ekpoma rice) had a balanced moisture content of 16.75%, offering an ideal compromise between freshness and storage quality. Its moisture stability helps preserve texture after cooking, a desirable trait for consumer satisfaction. Foreign sample F (12.61%) and I (10.97%) exhibited low moisture levels, making them more shelf-stable but potentially less soft after cooking.

7.2 ASH Content

Ash content reflects the total mineral composition of rice. Most samples recorded relatively low ash levels (0.3%–0.5%), except for F (1.87%), G (1.63%), H (1.83%), and I (4.3%), which indicated higher mineral presence typical of better-milled grains. The lower ash content in samples A, B, D, and E (each 0.3%) reflects fine polishing, which though aesthetically appealing, reduces mineral density. Interestingly, Sample E (Ekpoma rice), despite its low ash value, is known locally for its earthy flavor and balanced micronutrient retention, likely due to minimal over-milling. Sample I's high ash value (4.3%) may suggest over-retention of bran residues rather than genuine mineral richness. Thus, while foreign rice often boasts refined appearance, sample E represents a more balanced nutritional offering retaining essential minerals while maintaining palatable softness and aroma.

7.3 Crude Fibre Content

Crude fibre content in rice influences digestive health and satiety. Among the samples, fibre ranged from 0.33% (I) to 0.77% (H). Sample E (0.6%) showed a relatively high fibre content compared to most other samples, second only to H (0.77%). This is nutritionally advantageous, as fibre supports digestive regularity, helps control blood sugar levels, and lowers cholesterol risk. The slightly higher fibre in Sample E (Ekpoma rice) compared to other local and foreign varieties makes it an ideal choice for individuals managing diabetes or obesity. In contrast, samples such as I (0.33%) and G (0.37%) may digest more rapidly, potentially

causing a faster glycemic response. The balance seen in Sample E highlights its contribution to gut health and sustained energy release.

7.4 Crude Fat Content

The crude fat content across all samples remained low, ranging from 0.15% (Sample I) to 0.23% (Sample F), reflecting rice's naturally low-fat profile. Low fat levels are beneficial for cardiovascular health, as they help reduce cholesterol intake. Sample E showed a fat content of 0.19%, which aligns closely with the ideal range for healthy rice consumption. This amount ensures energy contribution without risking rancidity during storage, which is common in high-fat grains. Samples F (0.23%) and C (0.21%) had slightly higher fat values, contributing to a richer taste but potentially shortening shelf life. Overall, Sample E low and stable fat composition makes it suitable for individuals seeking heart-friendly, low-fat diets. Moreover, minimal fat content reduces oxidative deterioration, ensuring that Sample E (Ekpoma rice) maintains both quality and nutritional integrity over time.

7.5 Crude Protein Content

Protein content is a key nutritional parameter, determining the grain's dietary quality. Among all samples, B (14.65%) contained the highest protein value, suggesting superior amino acid compositions typical of enriched imported brands. Local varieties such as G (11.37%) and D (10.81%) also exhibited appreciable protein levels, while sample E recorded a moderate 8.45%. Despite being slightly lower than some foreign samples, Comparatively, C (7.91%) had the lowest value, indicating possible varietal differences and environmental influence on grain composition. Although the protein level of Sample E is moderate, this value is nutritionally relevant, as it still contributes to daily protein intake, especially in staple-based diets where rice serves as a major energy source. Importantly, moderate protein rice varieties like Sample E may be advantageous for individuals who require balanced diets without excessive protein load, such as those managing kidney health. Protein in rice also aids in enzyme production, hormone regulation, and immune system support. Thus, while not the highest in protein, Sample E remains a valuable nutritional resource with potential health benefits, especially when consumed as part of a diversified diet.

7.6 Carbohydrate Content

Carbohydrates form the bulk of rice composition and serve as the main source of dietary energy. Across the samples, carbohydrate levels ranged from 69.91% (B) to 74.87% (H). Sample E displayed 73.71%, ranking among the top energy-dense varieties, similar to A (73.22%) and I (73.58%). This high carbohydrate content makes Sample E a good energy source for both manual laborers and active individuals. However, excessive intake of high-carbohydrate rice may elevate blood glucose levels, increasing the risk of diabetes if not balanced with dietary fibre and physical activity. Fortunately, Sample E combines its carbohydrate richness with moderate fibre content, helping regulate glucose release and providing sustained energy. Samples with slightly higher carbohydrates, such as H and F, may be suitable for individuals requiring more caloric intake but should be consumed in moderation by those monitoring blood sugar.

7.7 CONCLUSION

The proximate analysis of the selected rice samples highlights the nutritional diversity present among varieties commonly sold in Benin city, with particular emphasis on the promising profile of sample (Ekpoma rice). Its moderate moisture content (16.75%) represents an ideal balance that supports good storage stability while maintaining kernel integrity and desirable cooking qualities. The comparative analysis of the nine rice samples reveals that both local and foreign varieties contribute uniquely to nutrition, quality, and consumer preference. While the imported types generally exhibited lower moisture content and slightly higher

protein levels, the local varieties, particularly Ekpoma rice (Sample E), demonstrated a more balanced nutritional profile, combining moderate moisture for pleasant texture, sufficient fibre for digestive health, and rich carbohydrates for sustained energy. Ekpoma rice stood out not just for its natural taste and softness after cooking, but also for offering a wholesome nutritional mix that supports heart health and helps regulate blood sugar, making it suitable even for individuals mindful of diabetes. The subtle differences in ash, fat, and protein across all samples highlight how soil quality, processing, and variety influence rice composition. Altogether, this study underscores that locally cultivated rice, when properly processed, can rival imported brands in both nutritional value and eating quality, affirming its potential as a sustainable and healthful staple for Nigerian households.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to express gratitude to the Centre for Atmospheric Research of the National Space Research and Development Agency, for the use of facility.

Conflicts of Interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

- [1] Abbas, A., Murtaza, S., Aslam, F., Khawar, A., Rafique, S., & Naheed, S. (2011). Effect of processing on nutritional value of rice (*Oryza sativa*). *World Journal of Medical Sciences*, 6(2), 68–73.
- [2] Abbas, A. M., Agada, I. G., & Kolade, O. (2018). Impacts of rice importation on Nigeria's economy. *Journal of Scientific Agriculture*, 2(1), 71–75.
- [3] Aderibigbe, A. T. B., & Eleduma, A. F. (2016). Water productivity and pig dung ash effects on upland rice (*Oryza sativa* L; cv-Ekpoma Local) grown in inland valley swamp (fadama) of Owo, Southwestern Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Engineering Studies*, 3(4), 1–8.
- [4] Adeyeye, S. A. O., Bolaji, O. T., Abegunde, T. A., Idowu-Adebayo, F., Tihamiyu, H. K., & Adebayo-Oyetero, A. O. (2019). Nutritional composition and heavy metal profile of Nigerian rice varieties. *Current Research in Nutrition and Food Science*, 7(2), 576–583.
- [5] Agric News. (2003). Rice is life. International Year of Rice, 2004 declaration. *Bayelsa State Ministry of Agriculture & Natural Resources*, 1(2).
- [6] Ahuja, S. C., & Ahuja, U. (2006, October). Rice in religion and tradition. In *2nd International Rice Congress*.
- [7] Ajala, A. S., & Gana, A. (2015). Analysis of challenges facing rice processing in Nigeria. *Journal of Food Processing*, 2015(1), 1–6.
- [8] Alens, O. P. (2017). Assessment of the use of surface water and its environmental health effects in Ekpoma, Nigeria. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 6, 2147–2161.
- [9] Andrus, J., & Mohammed, A. F. (1958). *The economy of Pakistan*. Oxford University Press.

- [10] AOAC International. (2000). *Official methods of analysis of AOAC International* (17th ed.). AOAC International. 1–2.
- [11] Aremu, M. O., Audu, S. S., & Gav, B. L. (2017). Comparative review of crude protein and amino acid composition of some leguminous seeds grown in Nigeria. *International Journal of Sciences*, 6(8), 1–10.
- [12] Basu, S., Roychoudhury, A., Sanyal, S., & Sengupta, D. N. (2012). Carbohydrate content and antioxidative potential of the seed of three edible indica rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) cultivars. *Indian Journal of Biochemistry and Biophysics*, 49(2), 115.
- [13] Bressani, R., Elias, L. G., & Juliano, B. O. (1971). Evaluation of protein quality. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 19, 1028–1036.
- [14] Chang, T. T. (1976). The origin, evolution, cultivation, dissemination and diversification of Asian and African rices. *Euphytica*, 25, 435–444.
- [15] Verma, D. K., & Srivastav, P. P. (2017). Proximate composition, mineral content and fatty acids analyses of aromatic and non-aromatic Indian rice. *Rice Science*, 24(1), 21–31.
- [16] Efisue, A. A. (2012). A comparative study on local and newly introduced rice varieties in Ebonyi State of Nigeria based on selected agronomic characteristics. *International Journal of Agriculture and Forestry*.
- [17] Eggum, B. O. (1969). Evaluation of protein quality and the development of screening techniques. In *New Approaches to Breeding for Improved Plant Protein* (pp. 125–135).
- [18] Eggum, B. O. (1973). *A study of certain factors influencing protein utilization in rats and pigs*. Copenhagen: Agricultural Research Laboratory.
- [19] Eggum, B. O. (1977). Nutritional aspects of cereal proteins. *Genetic diversity in plants*, 349–369.
- [20] Imolehin, E. O., & Wada, A. E. (2000). Meeting the rice production and consumption demand in Nigeria with improved technologies. *International Rice Commission Newsletter*, 49, 23–41.
- [21] Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO). (2000). *Agriculture towards 2015/30: Technical interim report*. Rome: FAO.
- [22] Fukagawa, N. K., & Ziska, L. H. (2019). Rice: Importance for global nutrition. *Journal of Nutritional Science and Vitaminology*, 65, 2–3.
- [23] GRiSP (Global Rice Science Partnership). (2013). *Rice almanac* (4th ed.). Los Baños, Philippines: International Rice Research Institute.
- [24] Harbinson, J., Parry, M. A. J., Davies, J., Rolland, N., Loreto, F., Wilhelm, R., Metzclaff, K., & Klein Lankhorst, R. (2021). Designing the crops for the future; The CropBooster Program. *Biology*, 10, 690.
- [25] Hart, F. L., & Fisher, H. J. (1971). Introduction—General methods for proximate and mineral analysis. In *Modern food analysis* (pp. 1–27). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [26] Hayashi, T., Nakamura, S., Visarathanonth, P., Uraichuen, J., & Kengkanpanich, R. (2004). Stored rice insect pests and their natural enemies in Thailand. *JIRCAS International Agricultural Series*, 13, 79.

- [27] Iloeje, N. P. (1982). *A new geography of Nigeria*. Lagos: Longman Nigeria.
- [28] Ismail, B. P. (2024). Ash content determination. In *Nielsen's food analysis laboratory manual* (pp. 129–131). Springer International Publishing.
- [29] Jabeen, A., Subrahmanyam, D., & Krishnaveni, D. (2023). The global lifeline: A staple crop sustaining two-thirds of the world's population. *Agriculture Archives: An International Journal*, 2(3), 15–18.
- [30] Juliano, B. O. (1993). Nutritional value of rice and rice diets. In *Rice in human nutrition* (pp. 61–84).
- [31] Kalpanadevi, C., Singh, V., & Subramanian, R. (2018). Influence of milling on the nutritional composition of bran from different rice varieties. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 55(6), 2259–2269.
- [32] Khush, G. S. (2000). Taxonomy and origin of rice. In *Aromatic rices* (pp. 5–13).
- [33] Maitah, K., Smutka, L., Sahatqija, J., Maitah, M., & Phuong Anh, N. (2020). Rice as a determinant of Vietnamese economic sustainability. *Sustainability*, 12(12), 5123.
- [34] Mangold, E. (1934). The digestion and utilisation of crude fibre. *The Imperial Bureau of Animal Nutrition*, 3(3), 647–656.
- [35] Mercer, D. G., & Peng, P. (2008). Solar drying in developing countries: Possibilities and pitfalls. In *Using food science and technology to improve nutrition and promote national development*. International Union of Food Science & Technology.
- [36] Mertens, D. R. (2002). Measuring fiber and its effectiveness in ruminant diets. In *Proceedings of the Plains Nutrition Council Spring Conference* (pp. 40–66).
- [37] Milena, L., Mandi, D., Kenjeri, & Piri, A. P. (1993). Intake of some minerals in healthy adult volunteers. *International Journal of Food Sciences and Nutrition*, 60, 77–87.
- [38] Min, D. B., & Steenson, D. F. (1998). Crude fat analysis. *Food Analysis*, 2, 201–216.
- [39] Moormann, F. R., & Juo, A. S. R. (1986). Present land use and cropping system. In *The Wetland and Rice in Sub-Saharan Africa* (pp. 191–194).
- [40] Nwokorie, E. C., & Ayogu, C. A. (2020). Acceptability of selected indigenous rice for sale in local restaurants in Nigeria. 350–359.
- [41] Odemerho, F. O. (1988). Benin City: A case study of urban flood problems. In P. O. Sada & F. O. Ode-merho (Eds.), *Environmental issues and management in Nigerian development* (pp. 97–111). Evans Brothers.
- [42] Ogundele, O. (2014). Factors influencing consumers' preference for local rice in Nigeria. *African Journal of Marketing Management*, 6(4), 49–55.
- [43] Oko, A. O., & Ugwu, S. I. (2011). The proximate and mineral compositions of five major rice varieties in Abakaliki, South-Eastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*, 3(2), 25–27.
- [44] Oko, A. O., & Onyekwere, S. C. (2010). Studies on the proximate chemical composition and mineral element contents of five new lowland rice varieties planted in Ebonyi State. *International Journal of*

Biotechnology and Biochemistry, 6(6), 949–955.

- [45] Oko, A. O., Ubi, B. E., Efiue, A. A., & Dambaba, N. (2012). Comparative analysis of the chemical nutrient composition of selected local and newly introduced rice varieties grown in Ebonyi State of Nigeria. *International Journal of Agriculture and Forest*, 2(2), 16–23.
- [46] Oluwaseun, O. A., Olalekan, O. S., & Adenike, A. T. (2024). The food security drive and the preference for local rice consumption among households in south-west Nigeria. *Nurture*, 18(4), 711–721.
- [47] Porteres, R. (1956). Taxonomie agrobotanique des riz cultivés, *Oryza sativa* L. et *O. glaberrima* Steudel. *Journal of Agricultural Tropical Botany and Applied*, 3, 341–856.
- [48] Ravichanthiran, K., Ma, Z. F., Zhang, H., Cao, Y., Wang, C. W., Muhammad, S., Aglago, E. K., Zhang, Y., Jin, Y., & Pan, B. (2018). Phytochemical profile of brown rice and its nutrigenomic implications. *Antioxidants*, 7, 71–87.
- [49] Sharif, M. K., Butt, M. S., Anjum, F. M., & Khan, S. H. (2014). Rice bran: A novel functional ingredient. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 54(6), 807–816.
- [50] Sharma, G. R., & Manda, D. (1980). Excavations at Mahagara 1977–1978: A neolithic settlement in Belan Valley. *Archeology of the Vindhya and Ganga Valley*, 6. Dept. of Ancient History, Culture and Archeology, University of Allahabad, India.
- [51] Solheim, W. G. II. (1972). An earlier agricultural revolution. *Scientific American*, 226(4), 34–41.
- [52] Sulistyowati, E., Rudijanto, A., Soeharto, S., & Handayani, D. (2020). The identification of characteristic macro- and micronutrients and the bioactive components of Indonesian local brown rice as a functional feed in obesity nutrition therapy. *Current Nutrition & Food Science*, 16(4), 494–500.
- [53] Thangaraj, P. (2015). Proximate composition analysis. In *Pharmacological assays of plant-based natural products* (pp. 21–31). Springer International Publishing.
- [54] Uko, A. U., Alagbaoso, C. A., & Osubor, C. C. (2020). Comparative analysis of nutritional composition of local and imported rice varieties in Nigeria. *NISEB Journal*, 20(4), 158–163.
- [55] Verma, D. K., & Shukla, K. (2011). Nutritional value of rice and their importance. *Indian Farmers' Digest*, 44(1), 21–23.
- [56] Whyte, R. O. (1972). The Gramineae: Wild and cultivated plants of monsoonal and equatorial Asia 1. Southeast Asia. *Asian Perspectives*, 15, 127–151.
- [57] Widyaningrum, I. P. (2022, March). The representation of rice in five selected Southeast Asian literature. In *Proceedings of the 10th Graduate Students Conference 2021: The Pandemic Imagination: Reading and Teaching Language and Literature in Time of Crisis*, 49.
- [58] Zibae, A. (2013). Rice: Importance and future. *Journal of Rice Research*, 1(10.4172).